

Final Test Algorithmic Thinking (JAVA)

Spring 2016

[15p] Question 1.

- a) What is the difference between an instance variable and a local variable?
- b) Name two differences between a constructor and a regular method.
- c) Take a look at the following signature:

```
private int countBigBalls( List<Ball> balls, int minSize )
```

For each of its components, explain its role/meaning in the signature:

i) `private`

ii) `int`

iii) `countBigBalls`

iv) `List<Ball> balls`

v) `int minSize`

d) Given the following variable declarations.

```
int a = 7;  
int b = 12;  
int c = 12;  
int d = 7;
```

Evaluate the following Boolean expressions.

- i) (a == c || a == b) _____
 - ii) (a < b && c > d) _____
 - iii) (a == b && b <= c) _____
 - iv) (a > d || ! (b == c)) _____
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[6p] **Question 2.**

a) Trace the variables **a** and **i** in the flowchart below. Use a table to keep track of each variable's value after executing each statement.

Statement	a	i
Start		
a = 0	0	
i = 1		1
i <= 6		1
a = a + i * i		
i++		
print a		
End		

b) What will be the output (printed in the console using **print**) of the algorithm specified by the flowchart above?

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[10p] Question 3.

Given is a scenario with Dodo and some RainbowEggs. Rainbow eggs can have any whole numbered value: negative, 0, or positive. There can be any number of rainbow eggs, from 0 to 100. Suppose the following method exists:

```
public List<RainbowEgg> getListOfRainbowEggsInWorld()
```

which returns a list of all the rainbow eggs in the world. The goal is to write an algorithm that **returns** the average value of the **non-negative values** (0 and positive) of the eggs.

- a) Specify the algorithm **using a flowchart**

b) Write corresponding **Java code**

[10p] Question 4.

Dodo is standing in the world at the location shown in the left picture, facing East. Her aim is to produce the egg pattern as indicated in the right figure.

Specify an algorithm which makes Dodo create the desired pattern as follows:

- a) First, give an algorithm `void diagonal(int length)` which produces one diagonal line of eggs.

- b) After that, use a while loop (with a counter) to create the entire diamond. You may give your solution as either a flow chart or as a Java program.
